

DEVELOPMENT OF STATE ENTERPRISES

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PhD senior lecture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260461>

Anotatsion: In this article, the processes of development of enterprises, specifically state-owned enterprises, are presented

Key words: organiztsion, enterprises, reorganizatsion, enterprise life

The activity of the enterprise consists of several cycles, which includes the following stages: organization of the enterprise; reorganization; restructuring; sanitation; bankruptcy and liquidation. It is not necessary to conclude that these stages apply to all enterprises. Because this depends on the result of the enterprise's activity. The existence of this process mostly depends on the financial stability of the enterprise. Therefore, in order to highlight the importance of ensuring the financial stability of the enterprise, we would like to briefly touch on the content of the above-mentioned enterprise life cycles. The first stage is the establishment and recovery of the enterprise. The rules of organization of the enterprise are given in the first paragraph of this chapter. In this rule, the foundation of the establishment of the enterprise is the property of its founder. An enterprise cannot be established without property. The use, improvement and maintenance of the property is carried out on the basis of ensuring the financial stability of the enterprise. The second stage is reorganization. In order to improve the enterprise's activities, increase its financial stability, maintain or expand its position in the market ("Niche"), reorganize such as opening new production or functional departments in its structure, adding some of them, merging them, liquidating ineffective ones. performs his work. In most cases, this issue arises from the financial situation of the enterprise. The third stage is restructuring. Restructuring can be considered as a form of reorganization. Restructuring is understood as separation of 4 structural departments (workshops) of the enterprise without the status of a legal entity, with an independent balance sheet and account number. The main purpose of this is to increase the efficiency of production, and the product (shop) of the enterprise is transferred to the commercial account. Property will be allocated to them, profits and expenses will be calculated separately. Sanitation is an activity that is organized by the founders (participants) of the debtor enterprise, the debtor's creditors and other persons, including the state, to restore the solvency of the debtor enterprise in order to prevent the bankruptcy of economically insolvent enterprises.

By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 362 dated July 26, 1999, the Regulation "On Sanitization of Economically Insolvent Enterprises" was adopted. According to this Regulation, the founders (participants) of the debtor enterprise - legal entity, the owner of the enterprise's property, state bodies and other persons can be the subjects of sanitization. The debtor enterprise is an object of rehabilitation. Such economically insolvent enterprises will be included in the list of objects to be reorganized, if the clear

possibilities of recovery of the debtor's solvency are based on the continuation of the activity. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, an enterprise sanitation fund was created. In addition to funds listed in the list of funds for the rehabilitation of enterprises, financial allocations of enterprise owners, creditors, associations (business associations), other legal and natural persons are also included. Sanitation is one of the measures to ensure the financial stability of the enterprise. The next stage is the bankruptcy of the enterprise. Bankruptcy of the enterprise is the consequence of its economic incapacity. Bankruptcy means the inability to fulfill the financial obligations of the debtor who has been recognized by the court or the debtor has voluntarily declared himself bankrupt, in short, financial incapacity. The Law "On Bankruptcy" (August 28, 1998, in the new version) was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Relations arising during bankruptcy of legal entities and individuals are regulated by this law and other legal documents. The last stage of the existence of the enterprise is its liquidation. On the basis of economic insolvency or bankruptcy, the activity of the enterprise can be stopped by a court decision or at the sole discretion of the owner. The liquidation of the enterprise begins at the moment of the termination of its activity and the entry of the debtor's liquidation into the state register, and the enterprise is considered liquidated. Economically insolvent enterprises can conclude a settlement agreement with other entities. Compromise agreement (compromising agreement) is an agreement between the debtor and the creditor to extend the term of payment of the debt or to cancel the debt. Decision No. 362 of July 26, 1999. 92 is an agreement on discounting. The settlement agreement is made in writing and is signed by the commercial court. 0 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 19, 2008. "On Approval of the Procedure for the Sale of Economically Insolvent Enterprises to Commercial Banks", a number of benefits (assistances) have been granted to restore the financial capacity of economically insolvent enterprises. certain opportunities have also been given to commercial banks through the document. President IAKarimov in his speech at the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers spoke about this as follows: "The activity of commercial banks in the financial rehabilitation of bankrupt enterprises transferred to the banking balance sheet due to unpaid debts deserves a high evaluation". Including: - establishment of a new enterprise with up to 100 percent charter capital on the basis of a bankrupt enterprise; - write-off of the unreimbursed loan given to the bankrupt enterprise in connection with its liquidation, including the amount of the loan granted with the Government's guarantee, by the decision of the bank board; - creation and involvement of a qualified management company for a bankrupt enterprise; - buying a bankrupt enterprise at the liquidation price, restoring its activity, selling it again at the market price, etc. Such a mechanism introduced by us is the introduction of additional investment by banks for the restoration of production activities in bankrupt enterprises, modernization of production, technical and technological renewal, ana Such enterprises are financially supported by J.Khodiyev B.Yu., Bekmurodov A.Sh., Gafurov U., 0 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IAKarimov "Modernization of our country and building a strong civil society is our priority" and "Our main task is the development of our homeland and our people 0 educational-methodological complex on the study of lectures entitled "is to further increase the well-being" - Tashkent: Economy. - 2010. 331 p. The experience of involving commercial banks in the process of recovery of loss - making and economically insolvent enterprises has fully justified itself in practice. It is necessary to liquidate the enterprises that are still working on the basis of old techniques and technologies, which have no economic prospects, and to

establish new modern production facilities on their basis. I.Karimov (from the lecture) envisages rehabilitation, introduction of production of new types of products and implementation of modern management methods, as well as restoration of jobs and creation of new jobs . In this way, enterprises that are able to operate, work at a much higher technological level than before, and whose activities have been revived, attract the attention of new investments more and more. Investors are currently actively buying such companies from banks. The fact that 140 out of 147 bankrupt enterprises transferred to the balance sheets of commercial banks today, and 64 of them were sold to new investors, is a clear proof of this opinion. It should be noted that the banks invested 156 billion soums for modernization and technological re-equipment of this enterprise, more than 21 thousand jobs were created. In order to imagine the importance of our work in this regard, I think it is enough to say that the production volume of these restored enterprises amounted to 460 billion soums, and various products with a total value of more than 165 million dollars were exported. Such an approach should remain the most important direction in the rehabilitation of bankrupt enterprises transferred to the banking balance in the future» Ensuring the financial stability of the enterprise is a multifaceted problem, many factors affect it. Therefore, its directions are also different. The following can be included among them: - effective use of the opportunities given by the state and authorities within the requirements of laws and regulations; - in-depth study of consumer demands and needs through marketing research; - regular analysis of competitive indicators and opportunities; - adapting the internal environment of the enterprise, operating conditions to the needs of the market.

Organizations management efficiency resources efficiency supply improve at the expense of increase can work release efficiency directly management process and management activity effectiveness garden. This is management system improvement and management economy to provide justifies of the company efficiency to increase the economy competitive to be and to growth big influence shows.¹

To ensure the financial stability of the enterprise, it is particular importance to determine and analyze the economic, including financial parameters (indicators) of the enterprise. For this, it is necessary to use a number of indicators .

¹ <https://www.researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/2833/1996>

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